

NERSC Technical Report no. 468

Technologies and collaboration for sustained Arctic Ocean Observing Systems (A00S)

D3: Avenues for funding large-scale deployments of A00S

Geographical distribution of Norwegian polar research costs for different ocean and land areas, shown as FTE (Full Time Equivalent) and percentage distribution between the regions. From Statistics Norway (Rørstad, 2024)

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Executive summary

The AOOS project is a planning and collaboration project under the Arktis 2030 programme, with the goal to strengthening the Norwegian role in development of ocean observations in the Arctic. The project will prepare a plan for implementation of a holistic Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS) that will serve different scientific disciplines, public services and facilitate innovation. This report presents results from analysis of funding mechanisms for development and implementation of ocean observing systems in general, which includes the Arctic Ocean.

In Norway funding for ocean observation mainly comes from governmental budgets allocated to ocean research projects and monitoring programmes. The governmental budgets are channeled through the Research Council of Norway (RCN), research institutes, universities, and international programmes (e.g. EU and ESA). The offshore industry contributes with funding to research and technology development that is beneficial for their offshore activities and also to advance ocean observing systems.

The cost and funding sources for Arctic research are summarized based on reports from NIFU and Statistics Norway. The summary shows that ocean research represents the largest part of all Arctic research. The funding of this research comes partly from direct allocation in governmental budgets and partly from competitive proposals to RCN, EU and other sources. The most important funding sources for Arctic Ocean observing systems are EU projects under Horizon Europe and projects funded under Infrastructure in RCN.

In addition, industry-funded projects can be a significant contribution because there is a market for ocean technology companies to produce sensors and platforms for ocean observation. In this market there is increasing demand for new sensors designed for autonomous underwater platforms and vehicles (AUVs) to support research, industry and public services. The Arctic region is interesting because of the expected growth in industrial activities, shipping and the need for environmental protection.

The following actions are recommended regarding funding of AOOS:

1. Establishment of a dedicated funding stream for sustained Arctic ocean observing, beyond the typical 3–5 year research project cycle
2. One funding route is inclusion of AOOS in national and European infrastructure roadmaps (RCN Infrastructure and ESFRI) to unlock long-term funding and political support.
3. Strategic alignment with Polhavet 2050 and International Polar Year 2032-33 to ensure that AOOS infrastructure and data systems are embedded in both programmes
4. Strengthening partnerships with industry and international collaborators, including leveraging co-funding models and shared infrastructure use.
5. Development of a governance and coordination framework to manage AOOS as a national asset with international relevance, ensuring continuity, data stewardship, and open access.

List of contents

1. INTRODUCTION 4

2. COORDINATION OF OCEAN OBSERVING IN THE ARCTIC 6

3. FUNDING OF POLAR RESEARCH IN NORWAY 9

 3.1 THE RESEARCH COUNCIL OF NORWAY (RCN)9

 3.2 STATISTICS ON POLAR RESEARCH FUNDING.....11

 3.3 INTERNATIONAL PERSPECTIVE FROM UNIVERSITY OF THE ARCTIC.....14

4. EUROPEAN FUNDING 16

 4.1 ESFRI ROADMAP16

 4.2 EUROPEAN COMMISSION17

Horizon Europe17

EU Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 203018

Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE).....18

JPI Ocean.....19

The Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership20

Copernicus Marine Service.....20

 4.3 EUROPEAN SPACE AGENCY21

5. OTHER NATIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL FUNDING SOURCES..... 21

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS 25

7. REFERENCES 26

1. Introduction

This report describes possible funding avenues for establishing a robust and sustainable funding framework for the deployment of the Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS). Such observing system is essential to safeguard both national and international interests in climate resilience, maritime safety, and environmental stewardship.

A fundamental prerequisite for implementing ocean observing systems in the Arctic is the availability of research infrastructure (RI), including platforms, instruments, and logistical services that enable personnel to travel and work in the region. Among the most critical resources are ships and icebreakers, which support measurement programs and facilitate the deployment and recovery of equipment and platforms in remote and ice-covered areas.

Norway offers extensive operational capabilities in the Arctic, notably through the icebreakers [FF Kronprins Haakon](#) and [KV Svalbard](#) (Fig1.1). The Norwegian Polar Institute is the owner of [FF Kronprins Haakon](#) while it is operated by the Institute of Marine Research (IMR). Its operational time is shared among three main institutions:

- 50%: UiT – The Arctic University of Norway
- 30%: Norwegian Polar Institute
- 20%: Institute of Marine Research (IMR)

This shared model ensures that the vessel supports a broad spectrum of national research priorities, particularly in the Arctic and Antarctic. Other institutions may rent the vessel at an approximate cost of 0.5 MNOK per day.

[KV Svalbard](#) and other Coast Guard vessels also serve as valuable assets for the research community. Norwegian research institutions can apply for ship time through the Research Council of Norway's dedicated program: "Forskningsstokt med Kystvakten og Havforskning". This program is especially important for institutions outside the [Kronprins Haakon](#) consortium, although regular users such as the Norwegian Polar Institute also benefit from it.

All these resources are directly financed by the Norwegian Government, while research activities and infrastructure are supported through various research programs (see Section 2).

[Longyearbyen](#) in Svalbard plays a key role in providing logistical support, accommodation, transport, and travel services for scientific activities in the Arctic. Many cruises in the Fram Strait, Barents Sea, and the Arctic Ocean begin and end in Longyearbyen, utilizing local logistics companies for storage, equipment shipping, and transportation. Some projects also access facilities at the Norwegian Polar Institute and UNIS. For research in coastal areas around Svalbard, including fjords and land-based studies, the [Svalbard Science Center](#) in Longyearbyen and the research stations in [Ny-Ålesund](#) (Fig. 1.1) serve as central hubs.

Operating ocean RIs in the Arctic is costly for several reasons: (1) Logistical expenses—such as storage in Longyearbyen and transport of equipment by sea or air—are substantial. (2) Vessels, including icebreakers, are required for both deployment and recovery of infrastructure. (3) Platforms and instruments must be designed for long-term operation (1–3 years) in harsh, ice-covered environments, which significantly increases establishment costs compared to RIs in other regions. (4)

Additionally, the risk of equipment loss is higher, necessitating contingency funding for replacements. The estimated costs for establishing and operating various AOOS modules will be presented in **Deliverable D5**, to be delivered towards the end of 2025.

Figure 1.1 (a) The Norwegian Coast Guard icebreaker KV Svalbard (photo by the Coast Guard); (b) Ny-Ålesund research station (photo by NySMAC November 2023).

The Arctic Ocean is bordered by five countries, and its waters are divided between national Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs) and the high seas, which fall outside any single nation’s jurisdiction (see Fig. 1.2). Within the EEZ the coastal states have responsibilities for observation and management of the ocean. The Norwegian areas (marked in yellow) cover large parts of the Nordic Seas, the Barents Sea and around and north of Svalbard.

Figure 1.2 Left: Map of EEZs in the Arctic Ocean which belong to USA, Canada, Greenland/Denmark, Norway and Russia. The map is provided by the [Arctic portal](#). Right: a diagram defining the [maritime zones](#) under UNCLOS (United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea), giving coastal states exclusive rights and jurisdiction over the exploration and exploitation of natural resources within these areas.

To chart a viable path forward for a sustained Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS), this report explores potential funding mechanisms by examining both national opportunities within Norway and international models and partnerships that can inform and support long-term sustainability. Successful funding and implementation of AOOS will require extensive international collaboration. A key framework supporting AOOS is the [Central Arctic Ocean Fisheries Agreement](#) (CAOFA), signed in 2018 by eight countries and the European Union. The objective of the Agreement is to prevent unregulated fishing in the high seas portion of the central Arctic Ocean through the application of precautionary conservation and management measures as part of a long-term strategy to safeguard healthy marine ecosystems and to ensure the conservation and sustainable use of fish stocks. Under this agreement, [the Joint Program of Scientific Research and Monitoring Framework](#) (JPSRM) was established in 2023. The JPSRM now includes an implementation plan, a secure data-sharing portal, and a publicly accessible website, providing a foundation for coordinated scientific efforts in the region.

In this report the various pathways to funding Arctic Ocean observing systems are explored. The structure of the report is as follows:

- **Section 2** presents the most relevant collaborative organizations that support Arctic research and infrastructure.
- **Section 3** describes Norwegian funding mechanisms for Polar research including ocean observing in the Arctic.
- **Section 4** summarizes European funding opportunities, with focus on European Commission programmes and the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) programme
- **Section 5** provides a brief overview of other international funding mechanisms.
- **Section 6** gives conclusions and recommendations

2. Coordination of Ocean Observing in the Arctic

Several organizations, including governmental and international bodies, play key roles in shaping and supporting Arctic observation systems, as described in more detail in report D1 (Sandven et al. (2024)). This report focuses on their contributions to financing and sustaining Arctic ocean observing.

The [Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks](#) (SAON), a joint initiative of the Arctic Council and IASC, facilitates multinational coordination across the full Arctic system—atmosphere, ocean, cryosphere, land, and communities. While SAON does not fund or operate infrastructure, it plays a strategic role in mobilizing support, aligning efforts, and advocating for long-term investment. Its [Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems \(ROADS\)](#) aims to guide coordinated planning and funding strategies across national and international efforts (Starkweather et al., 2021). SAON also complements global initiatives like GOOS and aligns with European Research Infrastructures (e.g., Euro-Argo, EMSO, ICOS), helping integrate Arctic marine data into broader environmental frameworks.

The [Global Ocean Observing System](#) (GOOS), led by UNESCO's IOC, provides global coordination for ocean observations. GOOS defines essential ocean variables and promotes best practices but does

not fund or deploy infrastructure. Its role is strategic, supporting integration of satellite, in-situ, and modeling systems.

In Europe, [EuroGOOS](#) serves as the regional GOOS alliance, advancing operational oceanography and fostering collaboration among marine institutions. Though not a funding body, EuroGOOS influences research agendas and supports the development of ocean services. Its activities are embedded within the [European Ocean Observing System](#) (EOOS), a strategic coordination framework initiated by EuroGOOS and the European Marine Board (Fig. 2.1).

EOOS does not operate infrastructure or allocate funding, but it plays a key role in shaping funding priorities and promoting sustained investment. The EOOS Roadmap 2023–2027 outlines a vision for a user-driven, integrated ocean observing system, advocating for a mixed funding model—national, EU structural funds, and private investment. EOOS also supports harmonization of funding across sectors and countries to improve efficiency and infrastructure lifecycle management.

EuroGOOS supports five Regional Operational Oceanographic Systems (ROOS), one has focus on the Arctic ([Arctic ROOS](#)). Their purpose is to enhance cooperation among institutions contributing to regional ocean observations and to integrate data into pan-European portals. In the Arctic context, EuroGOOS, EOOS, and SAON provide essential strategic coordination and advocacy. They help ensure that Arctic Ocean observing is embedded within broader European and global frameworks and that contributing institutions can align with evolving funding opportunities. Additionally, a Task Team is developing the [Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance](#) (ArORA), modeled after [GOOS Regional Alliances](#). ArORA aims to strengthen Arctic-wide collaboration in ocean observing. Like its counterparts, it will not serve as a funding body but as a platform for strategic alignment, data sharing, and integration of Arctic observations into global systems.

The challenges in securing long-term funding and achieving coordinated ocean observation across Europe are addressed in the EOOS National Focal Points Survey report (Lara-Lopez et al., 2021). The report showed that more than half of the surveyed countries lack mechanisms for sustained funding beyond five years, despite the critical role of ocean observations in supporting climate resilience, operational services, and marine policy, (Fig. 2.2 and Table 1). Marine monitoring is generally supported by national core government funding, especially for statutory obligations such as ocean health. In contrast, ocean observing activities—particularly those tied to research, innovation, and real-time decision-making—depend heavily on national, European and international project-based funding, making them vulnerable to short-term cycles and discontinuity.

Figure 2.1 Logos of EuroGOOS, European Marine Board and EOOS

Importantly, even legally mandated monitoring does not guarantee long-term investment, revealing a disconnect between policy obligations and financial commitment. This gap threatens the continuity and effectiveness of observing systems, especially in the Arctic where operational costs are high and infrastructure demands are complex.

The survey also highlights fragmented national coordination, with multiple ministries and agencies involved, often without a unified oversight mechanism. This fragmentation hampers strategic planning and efficient resource use, underscoring the need for stronger national and regional coordination frameworks.

Table 1: Distribution of funding for ocean observing and monitoring initiatives in Europe (Lara-Lopez et al., 2021).

Types	Definition	Funding
Ocean observing	“The sustained, coordinated and systematic collection and delivery of ocean data to a wide range of users across climate, forecast and hazard warnings, and ocean health applications, for example as coordinated under GOOS to support a diversity of stakeholders”	Governments: <50% National research: ~15% EU and intl. funding: ~22% No long-term funding for >60%
Marine monitoring	“The regular, coordinated and systematic collection of ocean data undertaken at the request of a statutory agency for a specific purpose and against a defined end-point (or target). It is mostly done with the intent to aid in management by providing relevant information against predefined targets and thresholds that can trigger a management response (e.g. MSFD, Water Framework Directive, Common Fisheries Policy, Marine Spatial Planning Directive).”	Governments: > 70% National research: Negligible EU and intl. Funding: ~11% No long-term funding for >55%

To ensure the long-term viability of the Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS), the following actions are necessary:

- Establish cohesive national governance structures for ocean observation.
- Promote harmonized and sustained funding mechanisms across sectors and countries.
- Align Arctic efforts with broader European and global initiatives such as EOOS, EuroGOOS, SAON, and the emerging ArORA Task Team.

These steps are critical to building a resilient, integrated, and sustainable Arctic observing system that can meet the growing demands of science, policy, and society.

3. Funding of polar research in Norway

3.1 The Research Council of Norway (RCN)

In Norway financing of ocean observing systems is provided mainly by the Research Council of Norway (RCN), which administrates an important programme, the National Financing Scheme for Research Infrastructure (INFRASTRUKTUR). This programme supports both the establishment of new infrastructures and the upgrading of existing ones, with funding decisions based on scientific quality and strategic relevance. Applications are evaluated through a competitive process, and projects can receive up to NOK 200 million. Preference is often given to research infrastructures on the ESFRI Roadmap (section 4.1). ESFRI Roadmap infrastructures and larger investments are often taken up at the ministerial/governmental level. The scheme is designed to support infrastructures that are of national importance, promote international collaboration, and enable open access to research data.

Several research infrastructure projects are presently funded by RCN, and some of them contribute to ocean observing system. Projects that have installations in the Norwegian Sea, Greenland Sea, Barents Sea, Fram Strait or the Central Arctic Ocean are listed in Table 2, showing that there are no ocean observing infrastructures in the central Arctic Ocean. Some of the projects have ended and have no clear financing to operate in the coming years. This shows that a system such as AOOS will fill a gap in ocean observing systems, because none of the existing projects in Table 2 have activities in the central Arctic Ocean.

It is a challenge to sustain funding after the end of contract with RCN, especially for infrastructures with high operational costs that cannot be fully covered by user fees or institutional budgets. The Infrastructure funding focuses on the “establishment” period which is five years, while the following five years (the operational period) requires additional funding from other sources. Another challenge is the growing demand for data infrastructure, driven by the rise of data-intensive research across disciplines. This includes the need for high-performance computing, data storage, and systems that comply with FAIR principles. Additionally, the competition for limited funds is intense, with many high-quality proposals going unfunded, highlighting the need for increased and more predictable investment in research infrastructure. RCN has prepared an updated version of the [Norwegian roadmap](#) for research infrastructure (Fig. 3.1).

Beyond dedicated financing schemes for infrastructures, different components of the AOOS could be partly funded through a number of different sources, but this approach must use a synchronized timeline for an observing system to be effectively implemented.

Table 2. List of Norwegian funded research infrastructure projects which involve ocean observation and are relevant for Arctic and Sub-Arctic areas. Some of them are included in European infrastructures (section 3.2).

Title	Description	Coordinator	Activities in Arctic or Sub-Arctic seas
ICOS-Norway	Norwegian contribution to the Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS).	The Bjerknes Centre coordinates the Ocean Thematic Centre	Ocean observing stations onboard RV Kronprins Haakon and coastal steamer MS Richard With
NorArgo	A Norwegian Argo Infrastructure – a part of the European and global Argo Infrastructure.	Institute of Marine Research	A network of Argo floats are operating mainly in the Norwegian, Greenland and Barents Sea
EPOS-N	Norwegian node for the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory	University of Bergen, Dep. of Earth Sciences http://epos-no.org/	No observing system in the Arctic Ocean yet. Plan to deploy OBS in the next period (2025 – 2034)
NorEMSO	Norwegian node for the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory	University of Bergen, Geophysical Institute	Observing systems are deployed in the Norwegian Sea, Greenland Sea and Fram Strait. Not in the central Arctic.
Arctic ABC	Autonomous drifting observatories deployed in Arctic ice covered waters	UIT – The Arctic University of Norway	Ice buoys have been deployed in the central Arctic Ocean and drifted through the Fram Strait with the East Greenland current.
LoVe	The Lofoten-Vesterålen Ocean Observatory (LoVe) is a cabled ocean observatory with additional autonomous nodes	Institute of Marine Research	Data collection at fixed nodes, five are cables and two are autonomous.
SIOS	SIOS is a regional observing system for long-term measurements in and around Svalbard.	SIOS Knowledge Centre in Longyearbyen	Ocean observing activities are located in the fjords and areas around Svalbard.

In addition to funding from the Infrastructure program of RCN, other funding programs can contribute to the AOOS such as the [Portfolio plan for Climate and Environment](#). This portfolio includes [Polar Research](#) where Norway signed the [Agreement on Enhancing International Arctic Scientific Cooperation](#) with 10 countries. RCN also provides funding through international programs such as [JPI Ocean](#), [NordForsk](#) and the [Belmont Forum](#), which can have topics of relevance for ocean observing in the Arctic (section 4). As a rule, such funding is time-limited, typically up to 3- 5 years. The budgets of these projects are too small to build and implement ocean observing systems, but they are important for funding PhD and postdoc positions, support field experiments, develop data analysis methods, and publish scientific results.

Norsk veikart for
forskningsinfrastruktur
2025

Figure 3.1 Cover page of the [new roadmap for research infrastructure](#) prepared by RCN

The funding of research in Norway, which includes ocean observation and marine research, comes from several ministries, of which the Ministry of Education and Research is the most important because it provides close to 50 % of the national funding for research in Norway (EU PolarNet 2,

2022b). The funding from the ministries is distributed to universities, RCN and governmental agencies. Of the polar research funding in Norway about 25 % is allocated through competitive calls from RCN (EU PolarNet 2, 2022a). The funding from RCN related to polar research, infrastructure and management tasks was 350 MNOK in 2023 and about 325 MNOK in 2024, allocated to Norwegian institutions. In addition, EU projects funded Norwegian Institutions with 49, 64, 64, 86 and 93.6 MNOK for the years 2020 to 2024 (pers. comm. J.B. Ørbæk).

The largest part is provided through direct allocations to universities and governmental agencies. They can use the funding to support environmental monitoring programs or to set up own research projects. Both ocean observation and marine monitoring are largely funded by governmental agencies, as indicated in Table 1. The EU Framework programs and other European programmes also contribute to funding of Polar research in Norway (section 3.3).

Ocean industries, in particular offshore energy companies, contribute to ocean research, ocean observing systems and data collection to build up knowledge about the marine environment where they operate. Ocean observation technology is a growing market where Norwegian companies have leading roles. Development of sensors, platforms and other technologies needed in the observing platforms are mostly financed through R&D projects, but companies can provide important funding, especially in cases where they see a market for their products. RCN has funding for projects which require collaboration between industry and research partners where industry need to co-fund the projects (see also chapter 5).

3.2 Statistics on polar research funding

Statistics on polar research is available in reports from [NIFU \(2024\)](#), [Statistics Norway \(2024\)](#) and [University of the Arctic \(2024\)](#). Selected information about costs and funding of polar research (both Arctic and Antarctic) are extracted from these reports.

The Statistics Norway report (Rørstad, 2024) quantified the amount of research in terms of FTE (full time equivalents) for three geographical defined areas: the high North, Svalbard and Polar regions which include both Arctic (Fig. 3.2) and Antarctic. This number is an indicator on how much work effort is allocated the polar research, broken down in scientific disciplines, geographic areas, year and sectors (higher education/university, institute and business). The total R&D expenditures and funding sources for Polar regions in 2022 are presented in Table 4.4 (in Rørstad 2024):

Figure 3.2 The Arctic part of the Polar research in the NIFU report

Table 4.4 Total expenditure to polar research by sector of performance and source of funding in 2022. Mill. NOK

Source of funding	Higher education sector	Institute sector	Business enterprise sector	Total	Share of total (%)
General university funds	317			317	19 %
Research Council of Norway	170	163	1	333	20 %
Ministries and municipalities	8	611		619	37 %
Industry	23	60	13	96	6 %
EU commission	34	41		75	5 %
Abroad	10	45		55	3 %
Other National Sources	69	100	0	170	10 %
Total	631	1 021	13	1 665	100 %

Source: Statistics Norway

The FTE breakdown into scientific fields for 2022 is shown in Fig. 4.8 (in Rørstad 2024):

Figure 4.8 Number of FTE related to polar R&D by fields in 2014, 2018 and 2022

The marine disciplines have the highest FTE, consisting of Basic marine biology (rank 1), oceanography (rank 2) and Fishery biology, marine resources (rank 4). The graph shows that ocean research has more funding than other disciplines in the polar areas, indicating that ocean observing systems are needed for different marine sciences.

The FTE broken down by sector and year is shown in Fig. 4.9 (in Rørstad 2024):

Figure 4.9 Current expenditures to polar research, by sector of performance in 2002, 2006, 2010, 2014 and 2022. Mill. NOK and fixed 2015-prices

Source: NIFU and Statistics Norway

The translation of FTE into NOK is shown in Table 2.1, which is used to estimate the total cost of polar research in Figure 4.9 (Rørstad 2024) for the higher education and institute sector, respectively.

Table 2.1 Cost of FTEs in the higher education sector and institute sector by major fields and research institute group in 2022. Mill. NOK

Major Fields in Higher education sector	FTE cost, MNOK	Research institute group	FTE cost, MNOK
Humanities and the arts	1.389	Social science institute	1.402
Social sciences	1.415	Environmental institute	1.503
Natural sciences	1.563	Technical industrial institute	1.807
Engineering and technology	1.444	Health trusts without university functions	1.545
Medical and health sciences	1.386	Primary industry institute	1.510
Agricultural sciences	1.543	Other research institutions	1.539
Total/average cost	1.433		1.579

Source: Statistics Norway

The reports by NIFU (2024) and Statistics Norway (Rørstad, 2024) show that research carried out in the Barents Sea (34%) and other Arctic ocean areas (22%) represent the largest part of the total cost of polar research (see figure in the cover page). The total cost for 2022 was 1665 MNOK, of which 1021 MNOK was spent in the institute sector, 631 MNOK in the higher education sector and 13 MNOK in the business enterprise sector.

3.3 International perspective from University of the Arctic

University of the Arctic (UArctic), a distributed network of about 200 member institutions from over 20 nations, represent a major contribution to Arctic research. Universities and colleges represent 70-75 % of the members, while the remaining 25 – 30 % are research institutes, NGOs, museums and governmental institutions. A recent report from UArctic (Aksnes et al., 2024) presents results of a survey of the number of Arctic research projects and the corresponding funding by UArctic members as well as from non-UArctic members. The survey is done for the period 2016 to 2023 for the Arctic Council member as well as countries with observer status (Fig. 3.3). The survey includes externally funded projects, not internal projects within the institutions. The classification of science disciplines in the UArctic report is different from the disciplines defined by Statistics Norway (in Rørstad, 2024). The two reports are complementary to each other, one giving the international perspective and the other the Norwegian perspective on Arctic research funding.

The contribution from each country is shown in Fig. 3.3, where the relation between number of projects and amount of funding varies a lot. The funding reporting is not very consistent because some countries report only projects and not funding amounts, such as Russia. Countries with relatively high internal funding, may have less need for external funding. The EU is characterized by relative high funding of few projects, in contrast to what is the case for each country.

Figure 3.3. Number of projects and amount of funding for Arctic research from 2016 to 2023 for the 15 largest contributing countries including the EU (from Aksnes et al., 2024).

It is interesting to compare the number of research project from the UArctic members with the non-UArctic members, as presented in Table 3. In the USA the majority of the projects are from non-members, while Canada, Norway and Sweden have a more balanced contribution from non-members and members. The other countries have the majority of projects from UArctic members.

Table 3. Number of Arctic research projects starting between 2016 and 2023 from non-member and member of UArctic in 8 countries (from Aksnes et al., 2024)

Country	No. of projects from Non - UArctic members	%	No. of projects from UArctic members	%	Sum Arctic projects
United States	3212	74	1073	26	4285
Canada	1881	55	1546	45	3427
Norway	673	47	757	53	1430
Sweden	422	50	409	50	831
Finland	42	18	183	82	225
Iceland	44	20	157	80	201
Kingdom of Denmark	40	19	161	81	201
Russia	335		X		335

The UArctic report presents a list of the top 20 funding organizations (Table 3) ranked according to number of funded projects starting in the period 2016 to 2020. These organizations supported 75 % of Arctic projects in 2016, increasing to 78 % in 2020. Information is updated for 2022, but funding data is lacking for some institutions.

Table 4. List of top 20 Arctic research funders showing number of projects starting in 2016-2022 (Aksnes et al., 2024)

Arctic research funders (2016-2022)	No. projects	Funding (mill US\$)	Comments
Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council (Canada)	2241	183	2022 missing
Directorate for Geosciences (US)	1808	1075	
Russian Foundation for Basic Research	1325		2022 missing for project, no funding data
The Research Council of Norway	1209	593	
Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (Canada)	454	43	2022 missing
Natural Environment Research Council (UK)	449	154	
Japan Society for the Promotion of Science	404	48	
Russian Science Foundation	317		2022 missing for projects, no funding data
European Commission/ European Research Council	301	745	
Canadian Institutes of Health Research	273	120	
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (US)	269	503	
United States Department of the Navy	262	208	
National Natural Science Foundation of China	260	29	2021 and 2022 missing
VINNOVA (Sweden)	250	67	
National Aeronautics and Space Administration (US)	228	11	2019, 202, 2021 missing for funding
Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (Germany)	227		no funding data
Swedish Research Council	200	118	
Fonds de Recherche du Québec – Nature et Technologies (Canada)	189	6	
Swedish Research Council for Environment Agricultural Sciences and Spatial Planning	181	66	
Northern Norway Regional Health Authority	177		no funding data

The report from University of the Arctic (Aksnes et al., 2024) presents the number of projects and amount of funding for Arctic research for the 15 largest contributing countries including the EU. The report shows that USA is by far the largest contributor to Arctic research, both in number of projects and amount of funding (Table 3). The contribution from different funding organizations shows that RCN is ranked 3rd after Directorate of Geosciences in the USA and the EU (Table 4).

4. European funding

In Europe the major funders of ocean observing are programmes under the European Union and the European Space Agency (ESA), the former support all types of research while the latter supports satellite Earth observation and other space-related research.

4.1 ESFRI Roadmap

The [European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures](#) (ESFRI) is key program to promote, develop and operate ocean observing systems on a European scale. ESFRI is a strategic instrument established by the European Council in 2002 to support the development of high-quality research infrastructures (RIs) across Europe. ESFRI identifies priority areas for investment through its Roadmap, ensuring that RIs address major societal and scientific challenges across disciplines. Funding of the RIs is a mix of membership fees, host countries, national/regional projects, European projects and other sources. The ESFRI report “Funding of Research Infrastructures” gives details about funding practices and challenges of 54 RIs across 19 countries (ESFRI 2024).

To receive status on the ESFRI Roadmap, an RI must undergo a competitive and structured application process that demonstrates its scientific excellence, strategic relevance, and feasibility. The proposal must be submitted by a consortium supported by at least two countries, including a lead country, and must align with ESFRI’s strategic priorities. It should include a detailed scientific case, implementation plan, governance structure, and financial strategy, including lifecycle cost analysis. Proposals are evaluated by independent experts based on their potential to address major European research challenges and their readiness for implementation. A Public Guide on how to prepare a proposal for the ESFRI Roadmap has been published (Fig. 4.1). Successful proposals are then selected as either ESFRI Projects (in the preparatory phase) or ESFRI Landmarks (already in implementation or operation), gaining visibility, political support, and access to funding opportunities.

In order to receive ESFRI Landmark status, RIs usually need to have formed a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), show progress towards an operational RI, and possess binding financial support from national funding agencies or ministries that, as a sum, can support the operational costs of the ERIC. Being listed signals that the RI is of strategic importance to European

10 October 2025

science and innovation, which can attract national and international partners, as well as investment from EU programmes like Horizon Europe. It also facilitates access to shared expertise, best practices, and collaborative opportunities across borders. Moreover, inclusion on the Roadmap helps ensure that the RI is aligned with broader European research priorities, enhancing its sustainability and impact over time.

4.2 European Commission

Horizon Europe

Horizon Europe is the European Union's key funding programme for research and innovation, running from 2021 to 2027, with a budget of around €95.5 billion. It aims to strengthen the EU's scientific and technological bases, boost its innovation capacity, and support policies that tackle global challenges such as climate change, health, and digital transformation. It is organised into three main pillars: Pillar I - Excellent Science, Pillar II - Global Challenges and European Industrial Competitiveness, and Pillar III - Innovative Europe. (Fig. 4.2). Various components of ocean observing systems are funded in marine projects under Pillar II. If observing systems are defined as infrastructure projects funding can be obtained through proposals to the Research Infrastructure work programme under Pillar I. An example is the series of JERICO coastal observing projects which started in the Seventh Framework programme and continued with funding from the Research Infrastructure programme (www.jerico-ri.eu). A [roadmap](#) for technological implementation of the JERICO-RI is in preparation, leading up to an ESFRI application.

Examples of two large Arctic Ocean projects funded under Pillar II are: (1) Integrated Arctic observation system: [INTAROS 2016-2022](#) coordinated by NERSC, with 50 partners and a budget of €15.5 million, and (2) Pan-Arctic observing System of Systems: Implementing Observations for societal Needs [Arctic PASSION](#); 2021-2025 coordinated by AWI, with; 37 partners and a budget of €15 million.

Figure 4.2 Structure of Horizon Europe programme.

Both projects have focused primarily on coordination, combining models and observations, stakeholder services, and data delivery chains. While extremely valuable, these projects provided **limited direct funding for sustained ocean observing infrastructure**, reflecting a broader trend where large-scale funding prioritizes consortium-building and service development over long-term system deployment.

In the central Arctic, nine mooring systems are currently operational under two projects:

- Arctic PASSION supports two moorings operated by the Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI).

- HiAOOS (funded with €10 million) supports seven moorings operated by NERSC, in collaboration with Scripps Institution of Oceanography, with additional funding from the U.S. Office of Naval Research.

Together, these moorings host approximately **400 instruments**, providing critical ocean observations and enabling the deployment of **Argo floats, gliders, and AUVs** equipped with hydrophones. However, these systems are only funded through **2026**, and their future is uncertain due to high operational costs and the lack of inclusion in long-term infrastructure roadmaps such as ESFRI or the Research Council of Norway (RCN). Without sustained funding mechanisms, maintaining these essential assets beyond the current project cycle will be challenging.

Under Horizon 2020 (2014-2020) and Horizon Europe (2021-2027) a total of 179 Arctic projects at the cost of €474 million are so far funded. In addition, 51 Polar projects at €100 million are funded, involving both Arctic and Antarctic research. Many of these projects deal with observing different aspects of the Arctic Ocean. Information about ongoing EU projects in the Arctic and Antarctic is provided by the [EU Polar Cluster](#), a network hosted by the [European Polar Board](#).

EU Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters by 2030

Launched in September 2021, [this EU Mission](#) is part of Horizon Europe with a goal to restore the health of Europe's ocean, seas, and inland waters by 2030 through a systemic, basin-scale approach. The objectives are to

1. *Protect and restore marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.*
2. *Prevent and eliminate pollution in ocean, seas, and waters.*
3. *Make the blue economy sustainable, carbon-neutral, and circular*

Key features of the Mission are the Mission Lighthouses, which are regional hubs in four major basins (Atlantic-Arctic, Baltic-North Sea, Mediterranean, Danube-Black Sea) to pilot and scale solutions. Furthermore, the Mission supports development of ocean Digital Twins, virtual models to simulate and predict ecosystem changes. A central part of the Mission is the Mission Charter, which invites Member States, regions, cities, and stakeholders to pledge concrete actions that support the Mission's objectives, with over [1,000 pledges](#) already contributing to the Mission, and a dedicated [Mission Portal](#) which enables progress tracking, knowledge sharing, and access to funding and partnership opportunities. The funding framework is over €7.7 billion mobilized across projects and partnerships.

Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE)

[DG MARE](#) is a department of the European Commission responsible for the EU's policies on oceans, seas, and fisheries. DG MARE and other related DGs (e.g., Climate Action, Environment, etc.) can contribute with funding to support Arctic ocean observing systems in agreement with [EU's Arctic policy](#), which has focus on sustainable development, environmental protection and international cooperation in the Arctic.

At present, DG MARE is supporting innovative projects with their European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund ([EMFAF](#)) program (2021-2027; €6.1 billion), which provides funding for the

sustainable exploitation and management of aquatic and maritime resources. Projects are funded through tenders and call for proposals organized by the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency ([CINEA](#)). Projects are not explicitly focused on the Arctic, but several topic areas are relevant for Arctic ocean:

- protection of marine biodiversity and ecosystems,
- supply of quality and healthy seafood to European consumers,
- economic and social vitality of coastal communities,
- innovation in the sustainable blue economy,
- maritime security towards a safe maritime space, and
- international cooperation towards healthy, safe and sustainably managed oceans.

DG MARE has also played a role in shaping ocean observing initiatives through various tools and forums geared towards defragmenting ocean observations.

JPI Ocean

[JPI Oceans](#) (Joint Programming Initiative - Healthy and Productive Seas and Oceans) is dedicated to research on marine issues and will develop long-term partnerships and structures to link marine research and general marine environment policy.

Established in 2011 by the Council of the European Union, JPI Oceans is a platform open to all EU Member States and Associated Countries who invest in marine and maritime research. It currently includes 21 member countries and supports a wide range of joint transnational calls, knowledge hubs, and strategic actions across all European sea basin. JPI Oceans provides funding for projects on topics such as marine and maritime technology, aquatic pollution, blue bioeconomy, underwater noise, and climate science in Europe for oceans. A dozen of calls for Joint Actions have been launched since 2011, each ranging from €3 million to €30 million (Fig. 3.3). JPI Oceans often co-fund projects with other JPis (e.g., [JPI Climate](#), [JPI Water](#)) and [ERA-NETs](#).

Figure 4.3. Joint Actions carried out by JPI Oceans from 2012 to 2024 ([JPI Oceans Strategic Framework, 2021](#)).

The Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership

The Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership ([SBEP](#)) is a major European initiative aimed at fostering a regenerative, resilient, and sustainable blue economy. It was officially established in September 2022 and is set to run until August 2029 with a total funding framework of €450 million.

The Partnership is coordinated by Italy, with Norway as co-coordinator. A total of 74 institutions from 30 countries and the European Commission participate, pooling research and innovation investments and align national programs at pan-European scale. The partnership funds projects through joint transnational calls. Projects should aim to foster innovation in areas like ocean observation, digital twins of the ocean, and sustainable blue food production. It is a goal to promote sustainable use of ocean resources while protecting marine ecosystems. The present and [third call](#) is titled “Digitalisation and Innovation for Resilient Marine Ecosystems, Businesses, and Communities to Strengthen the EU Blue Economy’s Competitiveness” and has a budget of €43.5 million.

Copernicus Marine Service

The [Copernicus Marine Service](#) is the marine component of the European Union’s [Copernicus Programme](#). It is funded to provides free, open-access, and science-based information on the state of the Ocean at both global and regional scales. The service issues regular calls for tenders.

Table 5. Comparison between EU Mission – Ocean and Waters, JPI Oceans and SBEP (summarized by CoPilot)

Feature	EU Mission: Restore Our Ocean and Waters	JPI Oceans	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP)
Established	2021	2011	2022
Scope	A goal-oriented EU-wide initiative with a 2030 deadline and broad stakeholder mobilization	Intergovernmental coordination of marine R&I across countries, providing a collaboration platform	Co-funded partnership to support innovation and policy alignment for sustainable blue economy
Main Goals	Restoration, pollution elimination, sustainable economy	Align national marine research strategies	Support innovation for a regenerative blue economy
Funding	€7.7+ billion mobilized	Estimated €100+ million coordinated	€450 million planned
Approach	Mission-driven, basin-scale, citizen engagement	Joint actions, knowledge hubs, ERA-NETs	Co-funded calls, policy alignment, innovation support
Tools	Digital Twin Ocean, Mission Lighthouses	Knowledge hubs, joint calls, strategic actions	Calls for R&I projects, stakeholder engagement
EU Programme	Horizon Europe (Mission Pillar)	Independent intergovernmental initiative	Horizon Europe (Partnership Pillar)

An extensive overview of polar research funding and application procedure in 20 European countries has been published by EU Polarnet (EU-Polarnet 2, 2022b), showing the role and contribution of each country to Arctic and Antarctic research.

4.3 European Space Agency

The European Space Agency ([ESA](#)) is an intergovernmental organization dedicated to the exploration of space. Established in 1975, ESA coordinates space-related activities among its 22 member states. Its mission includes Earth observation, human spaceflight, satellite navigation, telecommunications, and the development of launch vehicles. ESA operates a number of satellite programs, including the [Sentinel missions](#) which support the operational needs of the [Copernicus programme](#). The Sentinel satellites together with the satellites under the [Earth Explorer programme](#) provide crucial data for ocean monitoring, climate change, environmental protection and many other applications. ESA offers several funding mechanisms and programs that support ocean observing infrastructure, primarily through its Earth Observation (EO) initiatives

Norway became a full member of the ESA in 1987. Since then, it has participated in a many of the ESA programmes on voluntary basis. As of recent years, Norway's annual contribution to ESA has been approximately NOK 400–500 million depending on the programme portfolio and commitments. For the Earth Observation only, Norway's contribution is about NOK 150-200 million per year. The contribution includes participation in Copernicus, Earth Explorers (e.g., CryoSat, SMOS, Swarm), and innovation initiatives like the [Arctic Phi-Lab](#). which has open calls for Arctic-specific EO innovation projects. To find information about calls ESA operates the [Invitation to Tender portal](#), where all proposals are submitted.

The [Norwegian Space Agency](#) is the governmental agency with responsibility for all space-related activities in Norway and participation in ESA programmes. Based on ESA's geographical return policy, Norwegian companies and research institutions receive funding and other benefits through

- Contracts for ESA projects
- Access to ESA infrastructure and data
- Participation in ESA-funded R&D project
- Technology development and innovation opportunities

The participation in ESA's programmes gives a net positive return for Norwegian companies and research institutions.

5. Other national and international funding sources

There are various public and private organisations that support Arctic and ocean research and can in many cases contribute to ocean observing. The most relevant are described in this section.

[Nordforsk](#) was established in 2005 under Nordic Council of Ministers with the objective to facilitate for research collaboration between Nordic institutions. Nordforsk funds research on many topics that are important for the Nordic countries.

From 2009 to 2018 Nordforsk granted approximately NOK 2.1 billion through 49 calls and implementation of 323 projects and other activities (e.g. Nordic Centre of Excellence). After 2018 Nordforsk has expanded the thematic calls to address areas like climate, health and digitalization. [Arctic research](#) is currently supported through nine projects, covering topics such as oceans, freshwater, biodiversity, over-tourism, and minerals. These projects involve collaboration with North American partners.

The [Belmont Forum](#) is an international partnership of funding agencies, international scientific councils, and regional consortia dedicated to promoting transdisciplinary, transnational research on global environmental change.

The Forum has committed more than €300 million, launched 23 calls between 2012 and 2024 and supported 192 projects, involving more than 1,000 scientists and stakeholders from over 90 countries. Each project involves natural scientists, social scientists, and societal partners from at least three countries. The amount of funds for each call varies from €2.9 million to €52.3 million. The funds for each project varies from €0.2 million to €1.7 million. Research related to the Arctic has been conducted in [19 projects](#), but none of them involved direct ocean observation.

Industry-supported research. In Norway the offshore oil and gas industry has been a major contributor to ocean research over the last decades. The industry needs data and knowledge about the ocean environment as part of their exploration of the Norwegian continental shelf. Other industries, such as aquaculture and emerging offshore windfarms also need data for planning activities and monitor of the environment during production. The research is conducted through contracts issued by the companies to research institutions to collect and analyze data, develop methods and make recommendations for the companies. Ocean observing technology development often takes place through collaborative projects between companies and research institutions because such development is commercially important for many companies.

Research funding from the offshore oil and gas industry has been available through the government-sponsored programmes PETROMAKS 2 and DEMO2000 over the last two decades. These programs are coming to an end and new research in collaboration with industry is now part of other programmes with focus on innovation, including portfolio for energy and transport.

The major oil and gas companies, such as Equinor, has often framework agreements with universities and research centres to support their research and education activities over several years. Recently, Equinor signed an [agreement with five universities and Norwegian School of Economics \(NHH\)](#)

worth 380 MNOK over five years. This is part of Equinor's long-term academic programme over 15 years. Equinor also funds ocean technology projects directly, such as the [LoVe infrastructure](#).

The fisheries and aquaculture industry contributes with financing to a dedicated research foundation ([FHF - Norwegian Seafood Research Fund](#)) established in 2001. FHF is a state-owned limited company owned by the Ministry of Trade, industry and fisheries. It is financed by the industry through a levy on exports of Norwegian Seafood at 0,3 %. FHF's goal is to create added value to the seafood industry through industry-based research and development. FHF invests about 500 MNOK each year in R&D projects.

Shipping industry is active in research on the green maritime transition. In a private-public partnership with Government, the [Green Shipping Programme](#) was established in 2015 with the goal to reduce the greenhouse gas emission from shipping. A major funding is provided by [ENOVA](#), Norway's clean energy fund, which recently allocated 1.2 BNOK to green maritime projects. The programme has so supported 54 pilot projects addressing electric ferries, hydrogen and ammonia-fuelled vessels and infrastructure for green methanol.

An important programme where industry cooperates with research institutions is the [Centre for Research-based Innovation](#) (SFI), a programme under RCN that started in 2007 and is still ongoing, covering all research disciplines. So far about 60 SFIs have been funded with a total amount of more than 5 BNOK. If 20% of the SFI were dedicated to marine or maritime projects, tentatively 1 BNOK is provided from RCN. On top of that, industry partners were committed to contribute with own financing, tentatively 50 % of the RCN funding, which amounts to 500 MNOK.

Private foundations. There are a number of private foundations that support research in various fields, mostly in health research, but some also in ocean exploration and research. Two examples of foundations providing research vessels for ocean scientists are mentioned:

[REV Ocean](#) was established by the Norwegian businessman Kjell Inge Røkke in 2017. The idea is to build and operate an advance research vessel to conduct research on plastic pollution, climate change and ocean acidification, overfishing and environmental impacts of fishing. The vessel is in its final construction phase and is planned to be completed towards the end of 2026. During 2025 the company is hiring crew members. It is not yet clear how the company will collaborate with the ocean research communities.

Figure 5.1 The REV Ocean vessel
(www.revocean.org)

The Schmidt Ocean Institute is a private non-profit operating foundation established in March 2009 to advance oceanographic research, discovery, and knowledge, and catalyze sharing of information about the oceans. Since 2012 the Institute has operated R/V Falkor to support multidisciplinary oceanographic research and technology development.

In 2023 the vessel was replaced by a larger and more advanced vessel, [R/V Falkor \(too\)](#) which was the previous M/V Polar Queen owned by GC Rieber shipping company. With this vessel, the [first polar expedition](#) was organized to the Weddell Sea in January 2025. The vessels have completed 30 research cruises with participation from 84 institutions in 19 countries. The institute does not provide funding but offers free access onboard their vessel for scientists and students, including technical support during expeditions. In return data and outcome of the research should be shared openly.

Funding in USA and Canada. As shown in section 3.3 institution in the USA provide significantly more funding to Arctic research than any other country. The US Arctic Observing Network (US AON) is working towards well-defined networks of Arctic observations across US Federal agencies. The main agencies are (1) [National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration](#) (NOAA) including five line offices but primarily the NOAA Global Ocean Monitoring and Observing's [Arctic Research Program](#), and chaired by agencies including (2) [National Science Foundation](#) (NSF), (3) [Environmental Protection Agency](#) (EPA), (4) [National Aeronautics and Space Administration](#) (NASA), (5) [Department of the Interior](#) (DOI), (6) [Department of Energy](#) (DOE), and (7) [Office of Naval Research](#) (ONR).

An example of a long-term ocean observing is the [US Interagency Arctic Buoy Program](#) (USIABP), which started in 1979 and is part of the [International Arctic Buoy Program](#). Another mechanism is the NSF [Long Term Ecological Research program](#) (LTER) where long term observations are selected in various ecosystem types with renewal funding upon successful application (six year intervals). At present, 28 such sites have been established, including a coastal Arctic LTER site - the [Beaufort Lagoon Ecosystems LTER program](#) (2017-present) which is based out of three nodes along the Beaufort Sea coast: Utqiagvik (formerly Barrow), Deadhorse, and Kaktovik. An ocean-based polar LTER site, the [Palmer Antarctica site](#), has been in operation since 1990. Three LTER sites have been funded for over 40 years, from the inception of the LTER program in 1980 to the present.

Other programmes with long-term funding are [Ocean Networks Canada](#) (ONC) and the [Ocean Observatories Initiative](#) (OOI) in the USA. These are both large-scale ocean observing systems, but differ significantly in their geographic scope, organizational structure, and funding models. The OOI is fully funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation (NSF) and operates with a consortium of academic institutions, primarily led by the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (WHOI), with key roles also played by Oregon State University and the University of Washington. ONC, however, is primarily funded through a combination of Canadian federal government support, national research infrastructure programs and partnerships with various organizations, including Indigenous communities, industry, and international collaborators.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Strategic Funding for AOOS in Support of Polhavet 2050 and IPY-5

The Arctic Ocean Observing System (AOOS) is a critical infrastructure initiative that addresses the growing need for sustained, high-quality ocean observations in the rapidly changing Arctic. As highlighted in this report, current funding mechanisms—largely project-based and short-term—are insufficient to support the long-term deployment, operation, and renewal of observing systems. This gap is particularly acute in the central Arctic Ocean, where operational costs are high and infrastructure is not yet included in national or European roadmaps.

The recently launched **Polhavet 2050** program, backed by a NOK 1 billion commitment from the Norwegian government, represents a transformative 10-year national effort to understand and manage the Arctic Ocean as it transitions toward seasonal ice-free conditions. AOOS will be essential to Polhavet 2050's success, providing the **baseline data, long-term observations, and infrastructure** needed to support research themes such as climate dynamics, ecosystem change, security, and governance. Without a sustained observing system, Polhavet 2050 risks relying on fragmented or short-lived data sources, undermining its ambition to deliver actionable insights for policy and management.

Similarly, the upcoming **Fifth International Polar Year (IPY-5)** in 2032–2033 will be a globally coordinated scientific campaign to address urgent polar challenges. AOOS can serve as a **cornerstone infrastructure** for IPY-5, enabling Norway to contribute long-term ocean data, facilitate international collaboration, and showcase leadership in Arctic science. The ramp-up period for IPY-5 begins in 2026, aligning perfectly with the operational timeline of AOOS and offering a strategic opportunity to secure multi-year funding and integration into global research frameworks.

Recommendations

To ensure AOOS can fulfill its role in supporting Polhavet 2050 and IPY-5, we recommend:

- **Inclusion of AOOS in national and European infrastructure roadmaps**, such as the RCN and ESFRI, to unlock long-term funding and political support.
- **Establishment of a dedicated funding stream** for sustained Arctic ocean observing, beyond the typical 3–5 year research project cycle.
- **Strategic alignment with Polhavet 2050 and IPY-5 planning**, ensuring AOOS infrastructure and data systems are embedded in both initiatives.
- **Strengthening partnerships with industry and international collaborators**, including leveraging co-funding models and shared infrastructure use.
- **Development of a governance and coordination framework** to manage AOOS as a national asset with international relevance, ensuring continuity, data stewardship, and open access.

By acting on these recommendations, Norway can secure its leadership in Arctic science, support transformative research programs, and ensure that AOOS becomes a lasting legacy for both national and global polar research efforts.

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